

336.1

Vorobyova Elena Ivanovna,

Doctor of Economics, Professor,
Professor of the Department of Finance and Credit,
Institute of Economics and Management,
V.I. Vernadsky Crimean Federal University,
Simferopol, Russian Federation.

Blazhevich Oleg Georgievich,

Ph.D. in Economics, Associate Professor,
Associate Professor of the Department of Finance and Credit,
Institute of Economics and Management,
V.I. Vernadsky Crimean Federal University,
Simferopol, Russian Federation.

Korobynikova Olga Mikhailovna,

Doctor of Economics, Associate Professor,
Professor of the Department of Economics and Entrepreneurship,
Volgograd State Technical University,
Volgograd, Russian Federation.

**THEORETICAL BASIS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE INSURANCE MARKET
AND THE PRACTICE OF PROVIDING INSURANCE SERVICES
IN THE RUSSIAN FEDERATION**

This article examines the theoretical foundations of insurance market development, its operational characteristics, the importance of insurance coverage for ensuring economic and social stability, the practice of offering insurance services, and ways to effectively realize the insurance market's potential in the context of high risks affecting the socioeconomic environment of the Russian Federation. The authors assess the financial condition of insurance companies, study the dynamics of insurance entities, demonstrate the structure of insurance premiums, and analyze the financial results of insurance operations. The importance of the ratio of insurance premiums to insurance reserves, whose dynamics demonstrate the degree of client confidence in insurance companies, is highlighted. A rationale for increasing the number of voluntary life insurance transactions and the advantages of endowment life insurance are presented. Based on an analysis of insurance company operations, the authors highlight the potential of the Russian insurance market and the need for an integrated approach to the implementation of insurance products and services.

Keywords: insurance market, insurance operations, insurance service, insurance premium.

.1.

([7])

:
 ,
 1
 ,
 2 Γ 2
 ,
 ... Γ ...
 ,
 nZl
 ,
 n Γ n

— ; — ; — ; —

2.

2024 208 . 101 . 32,686 %
 (. 3)
 2017-2024
 73,139 % 62,981 %.

4

5—

. 4.

()

2017-2024

, . (

[10])

. 5.

()

2017-2024

([10])

2024 () 2024 3720,0 2017-2024 2441,2
 1701,6 () 2017-2024 6 45-190
 2024 2,3 () 2017-
 2022-2024 2023 2022 ()
 — 1435,0 468,3 25,777 % 2024 2023
 () 62,798 %
 () 2017-2022 3,5 2023 2024
 () 6.

2018 2017 2019 2018
 2020 2019 2021 2020
 2022 2021 2023 2022
 2024 2023
 . 6. () 2017-2024 , % ([10])
 2024 2023 () 58,782 % 2017-2024
 2023 (19,184 %)
) 2021 2020 (11,043 %)
 (0,069 %) 2019 2018
 () 7.
 () 2017-
 2023 () 25-33 % 2024
 54,654 % 2024
 10 % () 2024 50 %
 ()
 8, () 9.
 () ()
 . 2024

2017 2018 2019 2020 2021 2022 2023 2024

■ ■ ■ ■ ■ ■ ■ ■

. 7. () 2017-2024 ([10])

() ()

, 71,116% 2021-2024 ()

1289,6 .(9,3). 2024

() , 24,680% 2021 . 2024 () 501,8 ..

282,3 . , 2021 . 2022 2023 2024- , 2021-

() ()

2024 () , 3,751% .

2023 .

10, 2024 11— .

1571,2 .. 802,1 . , 2 , , 2017 .

2024 2023 (330,5 . 26,643%).

2022 (317,2 . 34,341%).

8. 2021-2024 , () [10]

9. 2021-2024 , % () [10]

. 10.

2017-2024

, ([10])

. 11.

2017-2024

([10])

326,0 2,1 2024 621,1
 (101,4 102,2 3
) (, 2)
 2022-2024 2023 2022
 2023 — 330,5 317,2 26,643 %
 34,341 %, 2024

12.

12.

2017-2024

([10]

2022

2017, 2018 2024

40 %.

2022 , 17,227 %

2024

), 10%.

(2024 5

(90%).

2021-2024

2022

(Big Data),

2017-2024

13.

.13.
2017-2024 , . ([10]).

4,5 2024 540,6 4 420
 2023 3- 2022 (202,0 2).
 2023 (135,9 33,569%). 2021 (42,3
 17,280%).
 2024 462,8 5 378,8 5,5
 (149,2 86,218%). 2023 2-
 43,583%). 2022 (140,5 2021
 (29,6 14,602%). 2020
 (. 14),
 (. 15)
 (. 16).

	605,4	677,3	810,1	879,0	996,3	1 128,8	1 398,1	1 654,3
	2 429,7	2 918,9	3 337,8	3 820,3	4 297,9	4 596,1	5 268,9	6 337,0
	0,2492	0,2320	0,2427	0,2301	0,2318	0,2456	0,2654	0,2611

. 14. 2017-2024
 ([10])

0,2.
 2023 (0,2654), — 2020
 146

(0,2301). 2024

0,2611.
26,1

.15.

2017-2024

[10]

(2020 + 2019).
4,3 % 88,8 % 2024 88,8 %.

90%.

0,23-0,27,

2017-2022

2021 2020 (), 2022-2024

2024 (.16).

2017-2022

2023

2024

2023 2024

	1 278,8	1 479,5	1 481,2	1 538,7	1 808,3	1 816,7	2 285,1	3 720,0
	1 448,5	1 831,1	2 078,6	2 415,3	2 750,5	2 921,5	3 274,7	3 974,7
	0,8829	0,8080	0,7126	0,6371	0,6574	0,6219	0,6978	0,9359

. 16.
2017-2024 , % ([10])

17.

. 17.
, % ([10]) 2017-2024

2024 8,0 % , 2024 2,5 %

2019- (7,9%) 2018- (7,6%)

148

2022 (4,6%).

2024 30,8 %.

2019 (33,1 %).

2018-2022 (19,5 %).

9,0%

2024

30,8

2019 (33,1 %).

2018-2022 (19,5 %).

.18.

) 2017-2024 , % ([10]

2020 (47,6 %),

— 2017 (54,9 %).

2024 (35,5 %),

— 2021 (43,4 %).

)

2018 (87,7 %),

— 2022 (93,8 %).

2024

87,8 %.

2017-2024 95 %.

2017 2024

2022

2017

2023 2024

2021-2024

1. 6: .—2024.— .59, 4.— .24-48.— DOI 10.55959/MSU0130-0105-6-59-4-2.—EDNFTBYTP.

2. //—2020.— .12, 3.— .76-90.—DOI10.31107/2075-1990-2020-3-76-90.—EDNLBRPEH.

3. // : , , .—2022.— 4(61).— .45-56.— EDN FVCBUK.
4. / . . . // : .—2022.— .26, 4.— .211-229.— DOI 10.26794/2587-5671-2022-26-4-211-229.— EDN GNZOYY.
5. / . . . // : , , .—2025.— 1(70).— .187-202.— DOI 10.29039/2312-5330-2025-1-187-202.— EDN MJSGZO.
6. // : , , .—2024.— 1(66).— .89-98.— DOI 10.29039/2312-5330-2024-1-89-98.— EDN CPIZOZ.
7. // .—2006.— 4(8).— .149-158.— EDN JWYXLF.
8. / . . . // .—2020.— .12, 1.— .105-116.— DOI 10.31107/2075-1990-2020-1-105-116.— EDN YTPAEW.
9. // : , , .—2025.— 3(72).— .75-89.— DOI 10.29039/2312-5330-2025-3-75-89.— EDN LTOPJT.
10. / .—URL: cbr.ru/statistics/insurance/ (: 14.11.2025).
11. // : .—2021.— .25, 3.— .102-126.— DOI 10.26794/2587-5671-2021-25-3-102-126.— EDN FEGPKJ.

SPISOK LITERATURY

1. Aleshina, A. Yu. Razvitie ustojchivogo strahovaniya v Rossii / A. Yu. Aleshina, I. B. Kotlobovskij // Vestnik Moskovskogo universiteta. Seriya 6: Ekonomika. — 2024. — T. 59, 4. — S. 24-48. — DOI 10.55959/MSU0130-0105-6-59-4-2. — EDN FTBYTP.
2. Bryzgalov, D. V. Perspektivy cifrovizacii strahovogo dela v Rossii / D. V. Bryzgalov, Yu. V. Gryzenkova, A. A. Cyganov // Finansovyj zhurnal. — 2020. — T. 12, 3. — S. 76-90. — DOI 10.31107/2075-1990-2020-3-76-90. — EDN LBRPEH.
3. Druzin, R. V. O tendenciyah razvitiya lichnogo strahovaniya v Rossii / R. V. Druzin, A. G. Barsegyan, E. A. Fedulicheva // Nauchnyj vestnik: finansy, banki, investicii. — 2022. — 4(61). — S. 45-56. — EDN FVCBUK.
4. Kalmykov, Yu. P. Vozmozhnosti uluchsheniya finansovogo obespecheniya institutov social'nogo strahovaniya v Rossijskoj Federacii / Yu. P. Kalmykov // Finansy: teoriya i praktika. — 2022. — T. 26, 4. — S. 211-229. — DOI 10.26794/2587-5671-2022-26-4-211-229. — EDN GNZOYY.
5. Nesterenko, S. A. Cifrovyje finansovye uslugi v usloviyah cifrovoj ekonomiki: tendencii, vyzovy i perspektivy / S. A. Nesterenko, E. A. Smirnova // Nauchnyj vestnik: finansy, banki, investicii. — 2025. — 1(70). — S. 187-202. — DOI 10.29039/2312-5330-2025-1-187-202. — EDN MJSGZO.
6. Norec, N. K. Analiz i perspektivy razvitiya strahovogo servisa na rossijskom strahovom rynke / N. K. Norec // Nauchnyj vestnik: finansy, banki, investicii. — 2024. — 1(66). — S. 89-98. — DOI 10.29039/2312-5330-2024-1-89-98. — EDN CPIZOZ.
7. Slepuhina, Yu. E. Finansy strahovyh organizacij: problemy upravleniya ... / Yu. E. Slepuhina, Yu. G. Fomin // Ekonomika regiona. — 2006. — 4(8). — S. 149-158. — EDN JWYXLF.
8. Spletuhov, Yu. A. Informacionnye tekhnologii na rossijskom strahovom rynke: vozmozhnosti razvitiya / Yu. A. Spletuhov // Finansovyj zhurnal. — 2020. — T. 12, 1. — S. 105-116. — DOI 10.31107/2075-1990-2020-1-105-116. — EDN YTPAEW.
9. Smirnova, E. A. Strahovaya sistema rossii: sistemnyj analiz problem i model' sovershenstvovaniya / E. A. Smirnova // Nauchnyj vestnik: finansy, banki, investicii. — 2025. — 3(72). — S. 75-89. — DOI 10.29039/2312-5330-2025-3-75-89. — EDN LTOPJT.
10. Strahovanie / Bank Rossii. — URL: cbr.ru/statistics/insurance/ (data obrashcheniya: 14.11.2025).
11. Tulenty, D. S. Pensionnoe strahovanie v Rossii: sovremennoe sostoyanie i vozmozhnosti transformacii / D. S. Tulenty, A. S. Ermolaeva, P. G. Raba // Finansy: teoriya i praktika. — 2021. — T. 25, 3. — S. 102-126. — DOI 10.26794/2587-5671-2021-25-3-102-126. — EDN FEGPKJ.

28 2025

2 2025